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Direct neutrino-mass measurement — status and prospects

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Why measure the neutrino mass?

It is one of the **last remaining unknown fundamental parameters** of nature!

- Neutrino oscillations: Leptonic mixing matrix and squared-mass pattern Δm^2 .
- Only obtain **lower bounds** on $m(\nu)$ — **no absolute scale**, which bears important relevance:

→ M. Sanchez (Wed)
→ P. Denton (Wed)

What makes *non-zero neutrino masses*, and *why are they tiny*? Is there a new mechanism at play?

Are cosmological data & models compatible with the minimal ν -mass scenario, or are we seeing *signs of new physics*?

→ A. Vicente (Thu)

→ V. Poulin (Fri)

→ Informing particle theory in extending the **Standard Model of elementary particles**

→ Informing cosmology in validating/improving the **Standard Model of the cosmos**

Three paths – different ν -mass observables

→ this talk

Beta-decay and electron capture:

$$m_{\beta}^2 = \sum_i |U_{ei}|^2 m_i^2$$

Kinematics of weak decays, assumes only energy-momentum conservation

Observational cosmology:

$$M_{\nu} = \sum_i m_i$$

Interpretation within Λ CDM cosmological paradigm

Neutrinoless double beta decay:

$$m_{\beta\beta}^2 = \left| \sum_i U_{ei}^2 m_i \right|^2$$

Assume Majorana nature of neutrinos

Kinematics of weak decays: the principle

$$\frac{d\Gamma}{dE} = K \cdot F(Z, E) \cdot \underbrace{p}_{p_e} \cdot \underbrace{E_{\text{tot}}}_{E_e} \cdot \underbrace{(E_0 - E)}_{E_\nu} \cdot \underbrace{\sum_i |U_{ei}|^2 \sqrt{(E_0 - E)^2 - m_i^2}}_{p_\nu}$$

effective electron
(anti-)neutrino mass:

$$m_\beta^2 = \sum_i |U_{ei}|^2 m_i^2$$

Fermi's phase space for β -decay (similar for EC)

Modern twist: mass eigenstates m_i and neutrino mixing matrix U

Key requirements:

- High-activity source
 - ✓ ${}^3\text{H}$ (β -decay): $E_0 = 18.6$ keV, $T_{1/2} = 12.3$ yr (4×10^8 atoms for 1 Bq)
 - ✓ ${}^{163}\text{Ho}$ (EC): $E_0 = 2.8$ keV, $T_{1/2} = 4570$ yr (2×10^{11} atoms for 1 Bq)
- Excellent energy resolution
- Low background

Direct ν -mass experiments: techniques

Calorimeters

- Cryogenic microcalorimeters, implanted source
- Energy measurement via **temperature change**

MAC-E filter

- Magnetic Adiabatic Collimation with an Electrostatic Filter
- Energy measurement via **high-pass filter**

CRES

- Cyclotron Radiation Emission Spectroscopy
- Energy measurement via **frequency**

The KATRIN experiment

70 m long beamline: ultra-pure gaseous T_2 source combined with high-resolution electron spectrometer

KATRIN: latest results

First five
science runs:

Rate increase

Background reduction

Statistical optimisation

Final optimised setting

3.6×10^7 events
ca. 20% of total
data set

- Maximum likelihood fit with common m_ν parameter in **59 data sets** (1609 data points)

KATRIN: latest results

see: Aker et al., EPJ C 84 (2024) 12,
Schneidewind et al., EPJ C 84 (2024) 494,
Acharya et al., EPJ C 85 (2025) 757

Combined best-fit value: $m_\nu^2 = -0.14_{-0.15}^{+0.13}$ eV²

New upper limit: $m_\nu < 0.45$ eV (90% C.L.)

Uncertainty breakdown dominated by **statistics**.
Main systematics are **source-related**; many **improvements** in new data & upcoming analyses.

KATRIN: outlook

- **Oct. 2025:** Completed **1000 days of data** at endpoint for projected sensitivity $m_\nu < 0.3$ eV (90% C.L.)

Analysis of **full data set** of ~230 mio. events is under way

- Exploiting **rich physics program** beyond neutrino mass: eV-scale sterile neutrinos, LIV, relic neutrinos, light extra bosons, general neutrino interactions, ...

KATRIN Coll.: Nature **648** (2025) 70, PRD **107** (2023) 082005, PRL **129** (2022) 011806, PoS ICHEP2024 (2024) 326, PRL **134** (2025) 251801, ...

- **2026:** Detector upgrade **TRISTAN** to cover full tritium β -spectrum → search for sterile neutrinos and BSM physics at the **keV scale**

Mertens *et al.*,
 J. Phys. G **46** (2019) 065203

Neutrino-mass beyond KATRIN

Direct neutrino-mass measurement beyond degenerate regime requires **novel approaches**.

Common challenges: energy resolution, background reduction, well understood radioactive source.

Common goals:

- ▶ *Differential* energy measurement (in contrast to KATRIN's *integral* filter) makes more efficient use of measurement time.
- ▶ *Atomic tritium* source avoids systematic uncertainty from ro-vibrational molecular excitations.

Physics Briefing Book, Physics Preparatory Group, Oct. 2025

H. Robertson / UW Seattle

Cryogenic calorimetry with holmium

Principle: Atomic de-excitation energy after EC process $^{163}\text{Ho} \rightarrow ^{163}\text{Dy}^* + \nu_e$ ($Q \sim 2.8$ keV)

Idea: A. De Rujula and M. Lusignoli [Phys. Lett. B **118** (1982) 429]

L. Gastaldo, U Heidelberg

Er161 3.21 h 3/2-	Er162 0+ 0.14	Er163 75.0 m 5/2-	Er164 0+ 1.61	Er165 10.36 h 5/2-	Er166 0+ 33.6
EC	EC	EC	EC	EC	EC
Ho160 25.6 m 5+	Ho161 2.48 h 7/2-	Ho162 15.0 m 1+	Ho163 4570 y 7/2-	Ho164 29 m 1+	Ho165 7/2- 100
EC	EC	EC	EC	EC, β	EC, β

→ **Low-temperature calorimeters with ^{163}Ho embedded in absorber:**

ECHO experiment: EPJ-ST **226** (2017) 1623

HOLMES experiment: Eur. Phys. J. C **75** (2015) 112

HOLMES and ECHo: technologies

- Same principle: source **embedded** in the detector
- Different sensor technologies: **TES** (Transition Edge Sensors) and **MMC** (Metallic Magnetic Calorimeters)
- Good energy resolution & linearity, background level
- Challenges: read out **large detector arrays** (limited activity/pixel), **pile-up**

TES response at different ^{163}Ho activities

Specific heat & ^{163}Ho concentration

EChO: results and outlook

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SEIT 1386

MAX-PLANCK-INSTITUT
FÜR KERNPHYSIK

MMC with ion-implanted ^{163}Ho , SQUID readout

Mantegazzini *et al.*, *NIM A* **1030** (2022) 166406

- **EChO-0**: 4 pixels loaded with ~ 0.2 Bq ^{163}Ho , 4 days
 $m(\nu_e) < 150$ eV (95% C.L.) and $Q_{\text{EC}} = (2838 \pm 14)$ eV

Velte *et al.*, *EPJ C* **79** (2019) 1026

- **EChO-1k**: ca. 200 mio. events from ~ 60 pixels
(ca. 45 Bq total)

$m(\nu_e) < 15$ eV (90% C.L.) and $Q_{\text{EC}} = 2862(4)$ eV

- **EChO-LE (2026-2030)**: target **sub-eV sensitivity**

20k channels - fabrication ongoing

microwave SQUID-multiplexing

> improve energy resolution

> better spectrum model

HOLMES: results and outlook

TES with ion-implanted ^{163}Ho , multiplexing readout
 Alpert *et al.*, EPJ C **79** (2019) 304

- **HOLMES**: ~70 mio. events from ~50 pixels (ca. 15 Bq total)
 $m(\nu_e) < 27 \text{ eV}$ (99% C.I.) and $Q_{\text{EC}} = 2848(7) \text{ eV}$
- Data-driven model of ^{163}Ho spectrum
 Ahrens *et al.*, arXiv:2507.09240, *subm. to JHEP*
- **HOLMES+ (2024-2027)**:
 define building blocks for “almost table-top sized” ν -mass experiment with **sensitivity < 100 meV**
 > improve multiplexing ($\mu\text{mux} \rightarrow$ kinetic inductance current sensors), production in 2026
 > developed low- T_c TES prototypes (2025), fabrication & testing of 4x4 array in 2026

Energy through frequency measurement

Principle: Cyclotron radiation emission spectroscopy (CRES)

Idea: B. Monreal & J. Formaggio, PRD **80** (2009) 429

Electrons in B-field emit radiation, frequency f encodes kinetic energy:

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{eB}{m_e + \frac{E_{\text{kin}}}{c^2}}$$

Phase I

PROJECT 8

First frequency-based ν -mass limit:

✓ $m(\nu) < 155$ eV (90% CI)

✓ no background observed above endpoint

Project 8 Coll., PRL **131** (2023) 102502

& Phys. Rev. C **109** (2024) 035503

Phase II

CRES - scaling for ν -mass sensitivity

Key points:

- Use of atomic tritium (no ro-vib excitations)
- High uniformity & precision of magnetic field B
- Large effective volume & measurement time
- Low background (not shown)

Amad *et al.*, New J. Phys. **27** (2025) [105006](#)

The Project 8 experiment

Target: 0.04 eV sensitivity — Phase IV

- Large-volume ($\sim 10 \text{ m}^3$ scale) **cavity** for CRES detection
→ resonance enhancement of low-power electron signal
- High-intensity source of **cold atomic tritium**
- Magneto-gravitational **trap** for tritium atoms
→ complex magnetic system

Next up: Phase III

- 1.5 m³ cavity operating at *low frequency* (natural scaling to large volume)
- $m(\nu)$ sensitivity of **0.3-0.7 eV** in one year
- Integrated field design with trap ready for atomic tritium

Credit: L. Thorne

Mainz Atomic Test Stand (MATS)

Credit: J. Formaggio

Cavity prototype and electron source (MIT)

Phase II:
 $\sim \text{mm}^3$ -scale
effective volume

Funded as part of the *Quantum Technologies for Fundamental Physics* programme, leverages QT to address **key challenges of CRES**:

Extreme precision of B- & E-fields

3D field mapping w. Rydberg atoms,
< 1 μT precision, < 1 mm resolution

Zou & Hogan, *Phys. Rev. A*107 (2023) 062820

Tiny radiated powers, $\sim\text{fW}$

Quantum-noise-limited superconducting amplifiers

Zhao et al., *SC Sci. Tech.* 36 (2023) 105010
& arXiv:2406.02455

Observe $\sim 10^{20}$ tritium atoms for $O(1-10)$ yr

Storage ring to avoid trap-loading losses, multiple CRES modules

K. Valerius | Direct probes of neutrino mass

CRES Demonstrator Apparatus (**CRESDA**), employing phased approach:

Test with H/D first, but concept T-ready

- **2021-2025 (CRESDA-0):**
Basic technology demonstration
- **2026-2030 (CRESDA Tritium):**
System demonstration, scaling, tritium readiness
- **Next decade:** Neutrino mass experiment
→ 100 meV → 50 meV → O(10 meV)
(at Culham/UK or similar facility, international collaboration)

Amad *et al.*, *New J. Phys.* **27** (2025) [105006](https://doi.org/10.1088/1751-8121/ab9006)

The PTOLEMY project

Goal: develop technologies for direct **detection of cosmic neutrino background** through capture on ^3H . (Weinberg Phys. Rev. 1962; Cocco, Mangano & Messina JCAP 2007; Betti et al. JCAP 2019)

ESPPU inputs (2025), <https://indi.to/FCW4f>

Working principle combines strong (gram-level) atomic tritium source on carbon nanostructure, CRES-type electron tracker, dynamic ExB drift filter, and high-resolution calorimetry.

$$E_{total} = q(V_{TES} - V_{target}) + E_{RF} + E_{cal}$$

→ G. Cavoto (Wed)

The PTOLEMY project

Intermediate goal: ν -mass measurement

(e.g., **150 meV sensitivity** with $O(10) \mu\text{g}$ ^3H mass, target resolution $\sigma(E) \sim 50 \text{ meV}$ over few tens of eV)

ESPPU inputs (2025), <https://indi.to/FCW4f>

Experimental challenges:

- Final states of tritium-graphene bound system \rightarrow modeling (cf. PRD 106 (2025) [053002](#) & [2504.13259](#))
- High levels (1-100 μg) of tritium implantation needed \rightarrow collab. with Culham/UK established
- Demonstration of complex end-to-end measurement chain (e.g. dynamic filter, CRES tagging)

PTOLEMY Demonstrator:

- Custom s.c. magnet expected at LNGS in 2026
- First test of filtering concept (grad. E-field tuned to a grad. B-field to select endpoint)

> [Apponi et al., IJNST 2022](#)

> [Farino et al., IJNST 2025](#)

> [Ammendola et al., 2512.19437](#)

From KATRIN to KATRIN++

Leverage facilities of KATRIN and Tritium Laboratory Karlsruhe as platform for **new technologies**:

- **KATRIN now:**

Integral, $\Delta E = 2.7$ eV, $bg = 0.1$ cps

More tritium would help, but ultimately need:

- **Differential* measurement (FWHM < 1 eV)**

*) meaning: non-integrating spectroscopy

- ✓ Better use of statistics
- ✓ Intrinsically low background

- **Atomic tritium**

- ✓ Avoid broadening (~ 1 eV)
- ✓ Avoid limiting systematics of T_2

see ESPPU input <https://indi.to/5TR9w> & arXiv:[2601.00248](https://arxiv.org/abs/2601.00248)

From KATRIN to KATRIN++

Goal #1: Sub-eV resolution for **differential** energy measurement.
Added benefit: Immune to MAC-E filter backgrounds!

Several promising technology options

Time-of-flight via electron tagging (e.g. CRES-type)

TEC test stand (U Münster)
 Demonstrated improvement of MAC-E resolution by factor ~10
 Salomon, Weinheimer *et al.*, in prep.

Transverse Energy Compensator (TEC)
 fast-ramping drift tube

$\times 10^5 \dots 10^6$

Quantum sensor array
 (MMC or TES)

Electron spectroscopy with external source on MMCs
 Kovac *et al.*, [NIM A, 2025](#)
 Next: demonstrator for magnetic guidance and thermal coupling

From KATRIN to KATRIN++

Goal #2: Joint development of Atomic Tritium Pathfinder

Primary technical goals:

- Demonstration of a supersonic cold source
- Demonstration of trap loading and storage

Many compelling scientific questions!

Tritium Laboratory Karlsruhe as ideal platform:

- Setting up dedicated modular gloveboxes
- Tritium supply loop for throughput of ~10 g/day (KATRIN now: 40 g/day)

Take-aways

- Massive neutrinos are a signpost to physics beyond the Standard Model. They bear relevance from particle physics to cosmology.
- Kinematics of weak decays offer model-agnostic access to absolute neutrino masses.
- Currently most sensitive technique: β -decay of (molecular) tritium
 - KATRIN 2025: $m(\nu) < 0.45$ eV (90% CL); data on disk for sensitivity < 0.3 eV
 - Key technology drivers for coverage of oscillation-allowed range: high-resolution spectroscopy & atomic tritium (\rightarrow KATRIN++, Project 8, QTNM, Ptolemy)
- Complementary method: Electron capture of ^{163}Ho
 - Order of magnitude improvement with new bounds (HOLMES 2025 & ECHo 2025)
 - Next stage: scale up microcalorimeter arrays for sub-eV sensitivity
- Bonus: Precision experiments now address rich physics programme *beyond* the neutrino mass (e.g., LIV, sterile neutrinos, new particles, non-standard weak interactions ...)

Special thanks to:

- Matteo Borghesi
- Gianluca Cavoto
- Joe Formaggio
- Loredana Gastaldo
- Ruben Saakyan
- ... and many other colleagues from the ECHo, HOLMES, KATRIN, Project 8, Ptolemy, and QTNM collaborations

Supplementing slides

Development of the field

ν mass from kinematics of weak decays

The **direct** method — even though such experiments actually do **not detect*** neutrinos!

- Based solely on energy-momentum conservation, no underlying model choices (e.g., Majorana nature of neutrinos or cosmological model)
- *In principle*: Weak decays involving any neutrino flavor (ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ) will do.
- *In practice*: Focus on ν_e (electron capture) or $\bar{\nu}_e$ (β -decay) — same, assuming CPT symmetry.

Effective mass	Upper bound	Method	Reference
$m(\bar{\nu}_e)$	< 0.45 eV (90% CL)	β -decay of ${}^3\text{H}$ ($Q = 18.6$ keV)	KATRIN 2025
$m(\nu_e)$	< 15 eV (90% CI)	EC of ${}^{163}\text{Ho}$ ($Q = 2.8$ keV)	ECHo 2025
$m(\nu_\mu)$	< 190.000 eV (90% CL)	Pion decay at rest	PDG 2025
$m(\nu_\tau)$	< 18.200.000 eV (95% CL)	Tau decay, from LEP (!) data	PDG 2025

With *neutrino mixing pattern* from oscillations, single effective mass (no matter based on which flavor) *determines* the whole system!

Muon- and Tau-based measurements suffer from fundamental uncertainties (“small differences of large quantities”); → discussion in Otten & Weinheimer, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* (2008)

Outlook: KATRIN with TRISTAN detector

Aim: Measure the **full tritium spectrum** to search for keV steriles at $\sim 10^{-6}$ admixture

Challenges: Energy range **x 400**, electron rate **x 10^6** , high energy resolution, control of systematics

Technology: Silicon Drift Detector (SDD) array with **> 1000 pixels**

replica beamline for system characterization

- ✓ Capacity to handle high rates ($> 10^8$ cps)
- ✓ Excellent energy resolution (160 eV @ 5.9 keV)

Timeline: Implement in KATRIN beamline for **measurements** during **2026-2027**

Sensitivity to keV sterile neutrinos

- Present direct lab-based constraints: mixing sensitivity $\sim 10^{-3}$ (e.g. from **KATRIN commissioning**, at reduced source strength)
- **KATRIN with TRISTAN detector** will reach $\sim 10^{-6}$ statistical sensitivity with few months of data
- Key systematics under scrutiny (hardware adaptations, dedicated measurements)

New direct bounds on light sterile neutrinos

KATRIN Coll.,
Nature **648** (2025) 70

- Sizeable improvement in statistics (x6 compared to previous release)
- Neutrino-4 claim excluded
- Synergy with short-baseline reactor experiments (Prospect, Stereo, DANSS)
- KATRIN bound dominates for $\Delta m_{41}^2 > 5 \text{ eV}^2$
- Expect further improvement of sensitivity with full data set

